

THE PURPOSE OF THE SPEECH ACT AND THEIR TASKS PERFORMED BY THE LANGUAGE

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Annatsiya. Ushbu maqolada dunyo tilshunosligida hozirgi kunda til taraqqiyotining asosiy manbai hisoblangan neologizmlarni semantikderivation, integrativ, lingvokulturologik, semantikkommunikativ, lingvokognitiv, funksional-pragmatik, psixolingvistik va sociolingvistik aspektlarda tadqiq etish yo'nalishlarida izlanishlar olib borilayotgani hamda lug'aviy birliklarning muloqotdagi ahamiyati haqida yozilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Leksik birliklar, til, o'rgatish, ijtimoiy, o'rganish, usullar, muhit, jarayon, salbiy ta'sir, tovushlar, transpozisiya, bilim, ko'nikma, malaka, aloqa

Аннотация. В данной статье исследования проводятся в направлениях исследования неологизмов, которые в настоящее время считаются основным источником развития языка в мировой лингвистике, в семантическом словообразовательном, интегративном, лингвокультурном, семантико-коммуникативном, лингвокогнитивном, функционально-прагматическом, психолингвистическом и социолингвистические аспекты, а также значение лексических единиц в общении.

Ключевые слова: Лексические единицы, язык, обучение, социальное, обучение, методы, окружающая среда, процесс, негативное влияние, звуки, транспозиция, знания, навыки, компетентность, общение.

Abstract. In this article, research is being carried out in the directions of researching neologisms, which are currently considered the main source of language development in world linguistics, in semantic derivational, integrative, linguocultural, semantic-communicative, linguocognitive, functional-pragmatic, psycholinguistic and sociolinguistic aspects, as well as the importance of lexical units in communication.

Keywords: Lexical units, language, teach, social, learn, methods, environment, process, negative influence, sounds, transposition, knowledge, skills, competence, communication.

In recent years, our country has gone on the path of innovative development aimed at radically renewing all spheres of state and social life, because in the current era, when time is rapidly developing, the state that relies on new ideas, new ideas, and innovation wins. In world linguistics, the problem of continuous innovation processes in the language system has never lost its relevance. Especially in the last decades of the 20th century and the first decades of the 21st century, there were drastic changes, radical changes, and unprecedented updates in various aspects of social life. Extra linguistic factors such as the reunification of Germany, the establishment of the European Union, the rapid development of information and communication technologies, the processes of globalization and integration have led to the acceleration of innovation processes in the German language vocabulary, the enrichment of the language through neologisms, as a result of which their special study is more has become an urgent issue.

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processes of globalization and integration have led to the acceleration of innovative processes in the vocabulary of the English language, the enrichment of the language through lexical units, because of which their special study has become a more urgent issue.

Currently, in world linguistics, research is being conducted in the directions of researching neologisms, which are considered the main source of language development, in semantic derivational, integrative, linguacultural, semantic-communicative, linguacognitive, functional-pragmatic, psycholinguistic and sociolinguistic aspects. Despite the fact that researches are being conducted on issues such as the role of everyday colloquial speech in the current German language system, the specific features of the development of its vocabulary, the creation of new vocabulary units through non-standard methods, and their variants, neologisms are. There are ambiguous situations and aspects that need to be studied in the context of conversational speech. In the recent period, the main attention is paid to the study of speech phenomena that express the conflicts in the language system in the science of linguistics. There are always conflicts in the language system that cannot be foreseen by any criteria.

The specific features of the development of its vocabulary, the creation of new lexical units through non-standard methods, and their variability, there are unclear situations and aspects that need to be study regarding the research of lexical units within the framework of colloquial speech. Expressiveness, emotionality, imagery, evaluation, etc., are important problems, because their solution provides an opportunity for a deeper study of the fundamental issues of the new lexical meaning. Also, while explaining the essence of new lexical units, the specificity of their semantics and the mechanisms of their creation, the process of the emergence of lexical units, the research methods of lexical and phraseological materials of different styles, it creates a basis for the comprehensive study of the new lexicon in texts and dictionaries.

The relevance of this issue is determined by studying the pragmatic factors of speech activity.

In world linguistics, innovative processes in the language system are widely studied based on the materials of different languages. During the past period, M.D. Stepanova, V.D. Devkin, E.V. Rosen, M.I. Umarchodzhaev, B.T. Ganeev, I. Ibrahimkhodzhaev, S.I. Alatorseva, S.I. Toshaliyeva, W.Fleischer, P.Brown, R.Baayen, B.Gardin and others were involved.

The members of the language-using society take advantage of these contradictions and create an innovation that represents a departure from the norm during a certain period of language development. However, innovation is not a mistake in the language, because the norm does not fully cover the activities of the language, all its practical applications.

Human experience is concentrated in information. People's memory, history and traditions are embodied in it. At the same time, it also carries a certain innovation in terms of strengthening the exchange of communication between individuals and regulating the processes of the emergence of words.

Each type of communication requires a specific situation. In fact, written mass communication is characterize by a communication situation in which the participants of the dialogue perform through a specific speech object. As a result, this type of communication takes the form of indirect communication, which is further complicate by the distance of the participants in terms of space and time and the presence of an intermediary person. The mediator plays an important role in the communicative act of written mass communication. For example, in written

advertisements that are constantly use in everyday life, a copywriting bureau is an intermediary. The intermediary receives the relevant content information from the advertiser.

The third feature of the external-relational aspect of the complex dynamic system of the language is combine with the second, that is, the use of the complex dynamic system of the language in the process of speech communication in accordance with the customs and norms of the community. The internal-structural aspect of the complex dynamic system of the language covers the concept of language as a construction system special attention is paid to the analysis of system elements and construction models of system elements and a system of relations special attention is paid to the study of connections of system elements. Information needs to be specified for different purposes. At the same time, the transmission of information through speech, first of all, leads to the formation of various texts, the use of correctly formalized and analyzed texts to one degree or another. In turn, the reception of information is determined by different levels of understanding. The purpose of the speech act comes from the tasks performed by the language. For example, various tasks of expression, various imaginations, requests, as well as tasks that are determined depending on the addresser, addressee, information and context are among them.

It is distinguish by taking into account the communication process from all sides, paying attention to speech creativity, the language and style of the "speech work", and the interaction between individuals in the exchange of information through the medium of language. At the same time, also a consistency envisages scientific research related to the generalization of the new lexicon and the study of new meaning features in the communicative act, which is one of the important areas in the aspects of general language practice.

In conclusion, communication is a social activity and belongs to the system of types of purposeful human activity. Therefore, it is a social phenomenon in terms of its occurrence, nature, development laws. The purpose of communication is social communication, which tends to influence society. In this way, the characteristic of human communication is determined. Relative completeness of thought in terms of content and grammar, in general, is the basis of any conscious communication. The main condition for the use of any language unit is its completeness in terms of form and content. This completeness is ensure by the legal connections of independent and auxiliary words. The first unit of language studied in the communicative aspect is the thought, which is the reason for its recognition as the initial category of any linguistic analysis. The interrelationship of language units is precisely the context that occurs simultaneously with the process of formation of each word, construction and thought. The use of any language unit requires the description of its immediate environment. In particular, it is required to analyze the complete thought as the smallest communicative link and device at the layer of the phrase.

REFERENCES

1. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг «Ўзбекистон Республикасини янада ривожлантириш бўйича Ҳаракатлар стратегияси тўғрисида»ги Фармони. // Халқ сўзи, 2017 йил 8 февраль. –№ 28.
2. Ахмедов Анвар. Тил луғат таркибининг янгиланиш жараёнлари лингвистик муаммо сифатида. Монография. Қарши. «Intellect» нашриёти, 2022. – 140 б.
3. Бушуй А.М. Историческое развитие языка как объект общей лингвистики // Вестник Каракалпакского Отделения Академии наук Республики Узбекистан. – Нукус, 2004. – № 5-6. – С.157-158.

4. Бушуй А.М. Язык и действительность. –Ташкент: Фан, 2005. –144 с.
5. Бушуй Т.А. Краткая история лингвофилософии. – Самарканд: СамГИИЯ, 2008. – 88 с.
6. Бушуй Т.А. Язык в системной структуре. – Ташкент: Фан, 2014. – 232 с.
7. Бушуй Т.А. Соотношение нового и старого в развитии семантики иносказательности (на материале немецкого языка) // Замоновий филология ва лингводидактика масалалари. Илмий мақолалар тўплами. 1-қисм. – Самарканд: СамДЧТИ, 2014 а. – С.11-13.
8. Бушуй Т.А. Открытость и динамичность системы языка // Современные гуманитарные исследования. – Москва: Изд-во «Спутник +», 2015. – №2. – С.70-73. 23. Бушуй Т.А. Язык и культура. – Ташкент: Фан, 2017. – 184 с.
9. Бушуй Т.А. Некоторые особенности актуализации лексического содержания слова в немецком языке // Германистика в современном научном пространстве. Материалы V Международной научно-практической конференции. – Краснодар, 2017а. – С.52-59.
10. Болотнова Н.С. Основы теории текста: Пособие для учителей и студентов филологов педагогического университета. – Томск: Изд-во Том. гос. пед. ун-та, 1999. – С.15-18; Бушуй А.М. Язык и действительность. –Ташкент: Фан, 2005. – С.41
11. Мейе А. Сравнительный метод в историческом языкознании. – М.: Изд-во иностр. лит-ры, 1954. – С.82-83.
12. Степанова М.Д. Словообразование в современном немецком языке: Автореф. дисс. ... докт. филол. наук. – Л.: ЛГУ, 1960. – 48 с.
13. Девкин В.Д. Немецкая разговорная речь: Синтаксис и лексика / В.Д.Девкин. – М.: Международные отношения, 1979. – 256 с.
14. Розен Е.В. На пороге XXI века. Новые слова и словосочетания в немецком языке. – М.: Просвещение, 2000. – 252 с.
15. Умарходжаев М.И. Центр и периферия во фразеологии // Известия АН. Серия литературы и языка. – М., 1980, Т.39, – вып. 2. – С.147-152.
16. Ганеев Б.Т. Ортофрония и аллофрония в языке и речи // Филологические науки. – М., 2004. – №3. – С.57- 67.
17. Ибрагимходжаев И. Сложение как способ образования новых и окказиональных слов в современном английском языке. Автореф. дисс. канд. филол. наук. – М.: МГПИИЯ, 1979. – 26 с.
18. Алаторцева С.И. Проблемы неологии и русская неография: Автореф. дисс. докт. филол. наук. СПб., 1999. – 40 с.
19. Тошалиева С.И. Ўзбек тилида окказионал сўз ясалиши. Филол. фан. номз. дис. автореф. – Тошкент, 1998. – 25 б.